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Application of Digital Technology for Sustainable Science Education delivery at Secondary School Education in Nigeria: A Qualitative Study

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Abstract

Modern teaching resources are a necessity, considering the fact that technology forms a greater basis of education in today's digitalized world. In modern education, knowledge is effectively imparted with the use of digital tools. Digitization of education provides a great avenue for developing a cognitive, resource based approach to enhance learners' skills, lifelong learning capability, and continuous education. Quantitative educational growth that has taken place in Nigeria has been quite vast, though its influence upon technological development has been minimal. With the education sector going through a number of reforms in ensuring efficiency, some challenges have persisted; hence, their solutions do not fully solve these problems, meaning there is growing advocacy for the digitization of the education system of Nigeria for promoting technological advancement. Digitalization opens up information to different possibilities in terms of dispersals, offering a kind of democratization of knowledge whereby learning is altogether more individualistic and collaborative. With the advancement of technology, today there are many tools that can make the culture of learning from being a purely academic activity to an enjoyable and enriching process. Education stands at an unprecedented threshold of innovation moving into the future, which, within a very short period, needs to race with technological advancement lest it lags behind.

Keywords: Digital Technology, Service Delivery and Science Education.

Introduction

Teaching is a profession that is undergoing a radical transformation occasioned by the integration of new technologies in it. Essentially, teaching refers to the act of guiding or instructing. Teaching has conventionally been perceived as the delivery of knowledge to learners in a classroom through systematic observation of instruction. According to Greenwalt, (2016), teaching also involves the manipulation of situations to influence the learner to want to learn a skill or gain insight on their own. This will improve technology use in the classroom and lessen some of the outcomes for teachers and students. Digital education has become one of the central topics of today's world, where proximity to information and people all over the globe has made it increasingly challenging to find reliable sources among those less desirable. It certainly has influenced present trends in learning and teaching. Modern education tools are at the very core in today's digitized world. Technology has become one of the pivotal points of modern educational systems, providing opportunities to apply cognitive resource-based learning approaches where skills are developed towards lifelong learning and continuing education. Digitization allows information to be disseminated through all levels by democratizing knowledge and making education collaborative and self-directed, according to Onyia (2021). There are tools available today that can transform learning from a traditional academic task into an interactive, engaging process with technological benefits.

Indeed, digitalization is the hallmark of the 21st century, and in this respect, the education segment is also evolving rapidly with new ideas almost daily. The Central Institute for Education Technology

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adaptation requires that nobody remain in the dark about how technology progresses and is enhanced. The digital technologies are causing changes that may be found not only in the world of labor but also in educational institutions independently of the strategic efforts to provide better quality of teaching and learning (Pandy & Misra, 2014). Digital technologies have reshaped education, and systems of education in the world over had to adopt an integration approach toward Information Communication Technology. While such integration has provided various accruing benefits that come with integration, it has also raised concerns on the question of quality of teaching and learning with ICT, especially on how education systems adapt to current technological trends.

Theoretical Framework

Technology Determinism Theory (Marshall McLuhan and Veblen)

Technological determinism is a theory that posits technology as a primary driver of societal change, suggesting that technological advancements shape social structures, cultural values, and human behavior. In the context of Nigeria, the application of digital technology has been particularly pronounced, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, which accelerated the adoption of digital life across various sectors. Maikomo et al. highlight that the pandemic prompted a significant shift towards digital interactions in Nigeria, revealing both the facilitators and barriers to this transition. They argue that while the urgency of the situation led to rapid digital migration, systemic and socioeconomic factors constrained the full realization of digital potential, thereby impacting individual and national development (Maikomo et al., 2021).

The role of digital technology in shaping educational practices in Nigeria further exemplifies technological determinism. The increasing reliance on digital platforms for learning has necessitated a reevaluation of educational policies and practices. Research indicates that while the integration of digital technologies in educational settings has the potential to enhance learning outcomes, it also raises questions about the adequacy of digital competencies among educators and students (Olofsson et al., 2019). This reflects the notion that the availability and implementation of technology can dictate the effectiveness of educational reforms, aligning with the principles of technological determinism.

Moreover, the influence of digital technology on economic practices in Nigeria underscores the deterministic view of technology. The adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Nigerian ports, as discussed by Onwuegbuchunam et al., illustrates how technology can transform operational efficiencies and competitiveness in traditional industries. However, the study also notes that the integration of ICT is hindered by various challenges, including infrastructural deficits and resistance to change, which highlights the complex interplay between technology and societal readiness (Onwuegbuchunam et al., 2021). This scenario reinforces the idea that while technology can drive change, its impact is contingent upon existing social structures and conditions.

In the realm of entrepreneurship, digital technologies have been identified as democratizing forces that lower barriers to market entry, particularly for female-led small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. The research by Pergelova et al. emphasizes that digital infrastructures enable broader participation in the economy, suggesting that technological advancements can reshape economic landscapes and empower marginalized groups (Pergelova et al., 2018). This aligns with the technological determinism perspective, where the evolution of technology is seen as a catalyst for social change.

In conclusion, the theory of technological determinism is vividly illustrated through the application of digital technology in Nigeria. The pandemic-induced shift towards digital life, the transformation of

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educational practices, the modernization of economic operations, and the democratization of entrepreneurship all exemplify how technology can dictate social change. However, it is crucial to recognize that the effectiveness of these technological advancements is often mediated by existing social, economic, and infrastructural contexts, which can either facilitate or hinder their impact.

Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the factors that influence the acceptance and use of technology. This model identifies four key constructs: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions, which collectively determine users' behavioral intentions towards technology adoption. In Nigeria, the application of UTAUT has been particularly relevant in various sectors, including education, e-commerce, and healthcare.

In the educational context, the UTAUT model has been employed to analyze the acceptance of digital learning tools among Open Distance Learning (ODL) students in Nigeria. Itasanmi's study highlights that performance expectancy and social influence significantly impact students' intentions to use digital tools for learning. The research utilized a quantitative approach, collecting data from 522 ODL students, and found that these constructs were crucial in understanding the behavioral intentions of students towards adopting digital resources (Itasanmi, 2022). This aligns with the findings of Abbad, who noted that the UTAUT model effectively captures the determinants influencing students' usage of e-learning systems in developing countries, emphasizing the importance of contextual factors in technology acceptance (Abbad, 2021).

Moreover, the UTAUT framework has been applied to assess the acceptance of e-commerce platforms in Nigeria. Riantini and Vional's work illustrates how the UTAUT model can be integrated with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to evaluate users' acceptance of online-to-offline e-commerce systems. Their findings indicate that performance expectancy and facilitating conditions play significant roles in users' intentions to engage with e-commerce technologies (Riantini & Vional, 2018). This is particularly relevant in Nigeria, where the growth of digital commerce is influenced by both technological advancements and socio-economic factors.

In the healthcare sector, the UTAUT model has been utilized to evaluate the acceptance of telehealth services among patients. Békés et al. developed a patient version of the UTAUT model to assess attitudes towards telepsychotherapy, identifying that perceived usefulness and social influence were critical in determining patients' intentions to use such services (Békés et al., 2022). This reflects the broader applicability of UTAUT in understanding technology acceptance in various contexts, including the Nigerian healthcare landscape, where digital health interventions are becoming increasingly important. Furthermore, the relevance of UTAUT in Nigeria is underscored by its application in assessing the acceptance of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in tertiary institutions. Aguboshim et al. argue that despite the potential of ICT to enhance research and innovation, poor policies and infrastructural challenges hinder effective adoption. Their study employs UTAUT as a conceptual framework to analyze these barriers and propose solutions for improving ICT acceptance in Nigerian universities (Aguboshim et al., 2021). This highlights the model's utility in identifying not only the factors that promote technology acceptance but also the challenges that need to be addressed.

In conclusion, the UTAUT model serves as a vital tool for understanding the dynamics of technology acceptance in Nigeria across various sectors. Its application in education, e-commerce,

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healthcare, and ICT illustrates the model's versatility and relevance in addressing the unique challenges and opportunities presented by digital technologies in the Nigerian context. By focusing on the key constructs of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions, stakeholders can better design and implement technologies that meet the needs of users in Nigeria.

Application of Digital Technology in Science Education Delivery in Nigeria

It includes but is not limited to all forms of digital tools, systems, and services, including software, hardware, data, and networks. This relates to all parts owned, leased, or licensed by any organization and provided for students, employees, or volunteers for access. Examples are computers, data servers, networks, cell phones, modems, email systems, the Internet, and other related technologies. Basically, digital technology employs a range of computer-based tools and technologies for dissimilar reasons in life, including education, the economy, as well as daily life. In education, it acts as a driver to educational innovation by revitalizing conventional learning methodologies. According to Joel and Min (2020), digital technology acts as an essential component of technological development impacting behavioral and economic patterns through change in current rules and systems. It can also be an agent of institutional change and catalyst as new structures and practices are introduced in a number of sectors. Digital technologies include tools, systems, and devices that can create, store or even process data. Examples include but are not limited to personal computers, tablets, cameras, calculators, and digital toys. Systems on the other hand are software, apps, augmented and virtual reality while intangible forms include the internet (Johnstone et al., 2018).

Application of Digital Technology through Information Delivery at Secondary School Level of Education

The modern digital environment is replete with affordances towards the dual objective of information delivery and user interaction. In a normal multimedia display, the user is presented with text, pictures and diagrams, sound, spoken messages, and input channels to enter data—all presenting varied learning opportunities. According to Norman, 2013, the critical dimensions of digital technology in information delivery are as under:

Interactivity: Digital technologies are interactive. For instance, in serious games, learners are placed into virtual environments with the possibility to interact with others through roles and actions. Old media, such as books, audiotapes, and films, are passive and non-interactive; they do not change based on users' input.

Adaptivity: Some of the digital tools adapt the information presented according to the behavior, knowledge or character of the learner. So, a game could provide options; however, in real sense it may not adapt to what the user decides. On the other hand, an intelligent adaptive learning program assesses and reacts to every action of a learner that is related to the task at hand, such as correct or wrong answers or decision-making trends.

Feedback: Digital technologies offer feedback on learners' performance that ranges from simple acknowledgments of correctness to detailed explanations of how to improve. The feedback can be immediate, as in a message that appears upon performing some action, or it might be long-term, as in progress reports over a full semester.

Choice: Many of the available digital tools afford learners the opportunity to self-regulate their learning by offering choices as to what to learn and how to learn it. Whereas some of the technologies constrain

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learners into very tightly defined structures of exploration, others, such as the Internet afford massively greater freedom for students to explore answers to their own questions.

Non-linear access: Digital technologies enable learners to approach information in a non sequential order. This, in turn, makes it possible to develop individual learning pathways. Whereas traditional linear modes rely on engaging all students in the same order, adaptive technologies reorganize that order of content based on trailers.

Linked depictions: The technologies create links among the diversity of the depictions concerning something in different media-text, audio, video, and also interactive simulations. Such links among diverse viewpoints permit cognitive flexibility and enhance learning.

Open learners' input: Learners are able to let others know about what they understand by natural language, drawing, or any other creative input is a way in which one can create something or be visibly engaged in learning.

Communication with others: Digital technologies provide a means for the communication between the learner and others, that is, other learners or experts in the subject domain, to be text-based. This is with email, chat, and discussion forums as well as interactions able with multimedia. This could also be extended with regard to collaborative learning, conversation agents, tutors, or even crowd sourcing.

Application of Digital Technology at Secondary level of Education in the Classroom

Digital learning would provide students with more access to knowledge, and the content could be tailored to meet the needs of each individual student. Using online technologies in a classroom could make a big difference in how much students perceive and retain from their lessons. Herold, 2016 End

Virtual Textbooks: These are digital learning tools with a whole lot of information in an interactive and easy-to-use format. In any case, school administrators have to make sure students have access to digital tools for using these resources at home.

Classroom Technology Tools: Technology can make learning both virtual and on-site much more effective. Flip Grid, Zoom, WhatsApp, and Skype are platforms through which student and parent engagement can be increased.

Flip Grid: An effective video-based discussion tool for any age group. It works similar to a normal discussion forum, the only difference being that it uses video instead of text. Instructors post video topics related to the lesson, and students respond by recording a video and posting their own. Flip Grid has increased accessibility and engagement of discussions compared to text-based discussions. It is also easy and has a free version available for teachers and instructors.

Zoom: Better known for video conferencing, this platform has been used a lot in these pandemic times for classes and meetings. With Zoom, the teacher can creatively invite virtual guest speakers or hold online parent-teacher conferences that will increase parental involvement.

WhatsApp: The social media site assists in interacting between students and teachers both inside and outside of school. Students are able to connect with their peers or individually with the teachers over academic matters.

Skype: Students can participate in an individual or group conversation using voice or video calls through Skype. They are also allowed to send instant messages and files to teachers, which will make the communication easy and more interactive inside and outside the classroom.

Benefits of Digital Technology in Science Education Delivery in Science Delivery at Secondary School level of Education

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Advantages of Digital Learning to Students and Educational Institutions: The advantages of digital learning to students and educational institutions are pegged on a variety of key reasons. The key benefits of digital technology in education, as noted by Hannah (2023), are:

Constant Availability of Materials: Digital learning means that one can get access to learning materials from anywhere and at any time. This flexibility in studying at any time gives students better time management of their study schedules and also allows interaction and sharing of ideas with a global community of students.

Collaborative: Technology integration into education brings both video conferencing, sharing of documents, and group work. This will help the students in their preparation for professional teamwork environments, too.

Access to More Resources: In a digital environment, the students will have access to additional resources that include lecture recordings and extra reading. In such a way, the student will go over areas of difficulty and additional information on his own and at his own pace, reinforcing learning.

Better Engagement: The insights into engagement availed by digital tools give a bird's eye view of whether the students are, in fact, engaged. This will help instructors find out if a student is struggling or disengaged and, therefore, intervene right on time for an improved learning experience.

Personalized learning: This is yet another great advantage of using digital technology in education. Digital technology helps educators in making learning personalized by adjusting the methodology of teaching to the preference and style of learning in which an individual student is most receptive; hence, improving the effectiveness of the learning process for that student.

Encourages New Learning Methods: Digital tools provide a completely different learning methodology, such as microlearning and gamification. These emerging methods are considered to be amongst one of the most effective teaching techniques. These techniques turn out to be even more influential when amalgamated with digital technology.

Workforce Preparation: Technology keeps on changing; students should go with the tide. Digital learning in schools can prepare them for their future career by introducing them to the tools and techniques that will be expected from them.

Building peer networks: Digital technologies enable the student to connect and collaborate with their peers. Such connections can be built in the class, but also from a distance, to develop a community of feelings for peer learning and teacher-student connections.

Encourages Accountability: Digital learning places the student at the center. Students take accountability in their progress, with a sense of control over what and how they study, though guided and counseled by institutions.

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Student Performance Tracking: Most of the digital tools and content support tracking of student performance in the form of test scores, assessment, and attendance at a granular level. This helps instructors identify trends that indicate areas where teaching and learning need to be improved.

Advantages of Digital Technology for sustainable Science Education Service Delivery in Nigeria

In the words of Ding, (2000), Oniya (2021), some of the key benefits of digitization of education include: **Increased access** whereby conventionally students and teachers had to be present in the same physical location for learning to take place. However, of late, with the induction of technology into education, it is possible to have instantaneous and convenient communication across great distances with just the click of a button. It has affected education to the extent that online degrees are possible. Traditional schools established in Nigeria have started offering some of their courses online, while other schools sprout up that operate wholly online, with students and teachers never once meeting face-to-face. The same technology has enabled cyber-schooling for kids in primary and secondary school to do their work in the comfort of their homes.

Increased Flexibility: Closely related to improved accessibility, the notion of flexibility via the internet leads again to a less rigid timetable. Traditional school settings bind students to visiting school at certain times. Sometimes this is impossible because of work or family obligations. Through an online class setting, course materials are made available and the student has the prerogative to study and complete class work whenever it fits into their schedule.

Introduction of Online Testing: With online education comes its share of online testing, quite useful for a whole host of reasons. Foremost amongst these reasons is the fact that online testing is impartial and quite fair. If a machine is grading your test and automatically correcting the wrong answers, it's impossible to show any signs of bias. Also, online testing might turn out to be an excellent solution for those suffering from test anxiety and getting distressed with taking tests in a room with a group of other people. Finally, all that is much better with those busy schedules who may find it tough at times to come to a testing center at a certain time.

Increased Ability to Address Special Needs: Academic life, in days of yore, was defined by very rigid classrooms. Each student went through the same life irrespective of differing needs or differing abilities. While such a setting pleased some students and could function well within the same, some students did not have their needs addressed.

It improves the capacity of a school in catering to the needs of different types of students. Children with hearing, speech, or vision impairments, and children mostly bound to a house, receive quality education on par with all other kids. One can also cater to the needs of students who have intellectual disabilities, social disabilities, or developmental disabilities through advanced technologies. Be that as it may, in spite of the differential needs of any given student, technology changes education for the better by improving our capacity to devise learning environments that work for all.

On-line Learning Content Availability: Earlier, learning was confined to the four walls of the classroom. Educationally helpful tools were essentially books or officially prepared videos. Another way in which the Internet has affected education is that anyone today can share their knowledge with the world through an educational blog post, e-book, or YouTube video. This, in turn, means far-reaching benefits for anyone learning anything.

Adaptability and Personalization: Learning spaces are increasingly aware that what helps a particular student learn may be virtually useless to another, and what makes no sense to one may be the only thing

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that fits into another. Everyone's brains work in a different way, and everyone has a different style of learning, yet everyone used the same textbook for years on end. It allows the integration of technology in education to promote leveraging, whereby a multi-tool approach can be accommodated and students can have different learning technologies right at their fingertips.

It improves concentration and assimilation: Activities carried out through digital and interactive tools raise students' concentration, and therefore they will absorb the concepts faster, improving learning. This kind of tool involves students in more practical learning with the objective of consolidating what was learned.

It favors critical thinking: The different sources of information that technologies provide introduce different opinions to the students. In this way, the information and communication technologies favor debates and acceptance of people's opinions. Besides, it allows them to get to know other cultures by exchanging ideas.

More class productivity, more teamwork: New classroom technologies, especially those allowing access to online content, improve learning productivity as they optimize instruction time; thanks to connectivity, they support teamwork due to new teaching formulae.

It motivates: The use of technologies in the classroom increases the motivation of young people; it is a fast and efficient methodology that develops the study of new knowledge. Digital tools represent the everyday communicative support of new generations, hence they are safely managed in this context.

It includes new learning methodologies: Another of the benefits of ICT in education is that teaching professionals can include new teaching methodologies, hence improving academic outcomes and encouraging dinamismo in the classroom. The use of such information technologies implies developing digital competencies with a view to avoiding digital divide.

Challenges of Using Digital Technology in Science Education Service Delivery at Secondary School level of Education in Nigeria

Technologies are not faultless; just as they bring many benefits to education, they have some disadvantages that have to be taken into consideration. Challenges include;

Inadequate Funding: Most learning institutions have been suffering from inadequate funding and resource allocation to education; most governments have not been able to provide enough funds to buy and maintain modern and current equipment to date.

Erratic Power Supply: Computerization and digitization can hardly take effect in an environment of epileptic power supply -Oniya, 2021. The issue of power has grown to be a national calamity. Hence, all the institutions in Nigeria depend only on a generator for power supply, and most often there is no light because there is either no diesel or generator breakdown, and this often hinders the process.

Poor Internet Connectivity: Internet connectivity is also one of the major challenges facing many educational institutions across Nigeria. It is obviously going to be very difficult to implement computer-based lessons and utilize various online resources in cases where there is a high level of power outages or limited internet access within a particular area, as confirmed by Mtebe & Raphael (2018). Lack or absence of internet connectivity will ensure that teachers and students are barred from accessing multiple online

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educational resources, software tools, and collaborative platforms that are so essential for their eventual success in computer studies education.

Lack of Modern Infrastructure: The state of infrastructural facilities in most Nigerian academic institutions is in disrepair. Yaya and Adeeko (2016) pointed out that ICT departments of these institutions are without modern computer systems; even the few available systems get infected with a virus which renders them not fit for digitization work.

Lack of Skilled Staff: Most academic staff are lacking even in basic computer training, let alone specialized training that may be required for digitization. Academic staff capacity in respect of equipment maintenance and software management needs continuous building.

Digital Distractions and Technical Overload: Living in a digital era, every student has to face distractions emanating from different digital tools and platforms that come their way (Rosen, 2012). The pervasive use of smart phones, social media, and online entertainment distracts students from attending to their tasks and assignments and hence decreased productivity and engagement.

Unsatisfactory Digital Literacy Skills: Even though children and students have lived in a world that is already saturated with technologies, most of them do not acquire adequate digital skills, which computer studies education demands (Fraillon, 2014).

Over Influence: Improper and excessive practice will bind students to an obsessive mentality with computer technology; this can cause them to fail to control consumption, hence affecting the student's health, social life, family life, and further deterring their academic performance.

It Limits the Development of Other Skills: Widespread use of digitalization in educational sectors can nullify some practices such as writing, public speaking, and reasoning. Proof of this aspect is shown by a recent study led by the University of California: "The report says that social skills among new generations will be based on this digital environment, hence affecting personal communication directly.

Personal Data Theft: In case of minor children, pupils might, out of ignorance about the potential risks of cybercrime, involuntarily give away their data by posting pictures with unknown people.

It Reduces Human Interaction: Through the use of newer technologies, the process of learning is being kept further and the human contact with the teachers and classmates reduces. Due to this, there can be possible isolation after the reduction of human contact, which will work as an obstacle toward the personal development of students.

It amplifies bullying: It is a sensitive topic and one of the main perils associated with it. The absence of physical interaction can grow into loss of confidence, and abuse of online tools and platforms can create incidents of digital bullying.

Conclusion

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The role of digital technologies in upgrading the delivery of services in education, particularly in science, cannot be underestimated. Digitalization did not make the brick-and-mortar classroom less important; it actually complemented the traditional concept. That is, a combination of both approaches yields a complete educational experience. It is only then that 21st-century education realizes its full potential: face-to-face instruction in combination with flexibility and access, realized by digital learning tools. This makes for dynamic learning environments that guarantee better engagement and deeper comprehension, leading to meaningful changes in schools.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusion, this study therefore recommends that;

1. Schools should make use of digital technologies while teaching or facilitating learning.
2. The government and all other stakeholders in education should ensure that digital technologies are sufficiently provided to schools.
3. Teachers need training on the effective use of digital technologies during instructions.
4. Investment in the improvement of school infrastructure must be done by the educational stakeholders.
5. More computer experts with professional skills should be hired by the government.
6. Access to the internet should be ensured for seamless connectivity.

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